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Automation and Income Inequality in Europe*

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Abstract

We study the effects of robot penetration on income inequality in 14 European countries between 2006-2018, a period of rapid adoption of robots. We first use the approach proposed by Acemoglu and Restrepo (2022) to show that, similarly to the U.S., automation reduced hourly wages and employment in Western Europe, but had no significant effect in Eastern Europe, where labor costs have been noticeably lower. We then use the estimated wage and employment shocks as input to the EUROMOD microsimulation model to assess how robot-driven shocks affected household income inequality. Automation widened income inequality in European countries, but its contribution was very small, about one percent of the recorded change in the Gini index in this period. European countries' tax and benefit systems absorbed wage and employment shocks caused by automation. Benefits played a larger role, especially in Western Europe. Welfare states appear more effective in mitigating the effects of automation in Europe than in the U.S.

JEL codes: J24, O33, J23

Keywords: robots, automation, tasks, inequality, microsimulation

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1 Introduction

The rapid automation of tasks previously performed by workers raises concerns about the effects of automation on workers' welfare. Robots, computers, and other information and communication technologies (ICT) increased productivity and average wages (Cardona, Kretschmer, and Strobel, 2013; Graetz and Michaels, 2018). Still, they partly replaced humans in performing routine tasks and reduced demand for middle-skilled labor (Autor, Levy, and Murnane, 2003). This led to job and wage polarization and widened wage inequality in many developed countries (Goos, Manning, and Salomons, 2014; Spitz-Oener, 2006). Acemoglu and Restrepo (2022) attributed more than 50 percent of changes in wage inequality in the U.S. over the last 40 years to wage declines of workers exposed to automation. Moreover, robot adoption reduced total employment in the US (Acemoglu and Restrepo, 2020). In other highly developed countries, such as Germany or Japan, the total employment effects have been neutral or positive (Adachi, Kawaguchi, and Saito, 2022; Dauth et al., 2021). Still, the employment prospects of some workers, for instance, young people in manual occupations, deteriorated.

As automation creates winners and losers in labor markets, its redistributive effects are key for understanding the effect on welfare.¹ Moreover, a household composition that facilitates sharing of labor market risks, progressive taxation, and social transfers may mitigate the effect of adverse labor market shocks on household disposable incomes. Whether and how much automation has impacted income inequality, and what has been the role of welfare states in cushioning it, remains an open question. It is of key importance from a policy perspective, as household incomes rather than wages are the ultimate targets of tax-benefit policies. Inequality of household income translates into societal perceptions of inequality, which in turn drive the demand for redistribution (Bussolo et al., 2021).

We answer this question by assessing the effect of industrial robots on household income inequality in 14 European countries between 2006 and 2018.² We focus on the penetration of robots as our measure of automation for three reasons. First, robots are usually implemented to improve efficiency in performing existing tasks and so have a clear task displacement component (Acemoglu and Restrepo, 2020). This distinguishes robots from general ICT technologies, which enable communication, data storage, etc., and more often create new tasks to be performed by people. Second, robots and specialized machinery predominantly drove changes in the wage structure in the U.S. (Acemoglu and Restrepo, 2022). It is important to evaluate if Europe follows the same or a different pattern. Third, the use of robots is rapidly increasing: according to the International Federation of Robotics data (IFR, 2021), between 2006 and 2018, the operational stock of robots in Europe increased by more than 80%, and its growth has accelerated after 2015 (Figure 1).

¹For instance, Aksoy, Özcan, and Philipp (2021) found that robot adoption increases wages for both men and women, but also widens the gender pay gap within sectors and occupations in Europe.

²Belgium, France, Germany, Netherlands, Sweden (Western European countries), Bulgaria, Czechia, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, and Slovakia (Eastern European countries).

Figure 1. Robots in Europe

Notes: Figure shows the operational stock of robots in 14 European countries. The shaded area covers the period of our analysis (2006-2018).

Data: IFR.

To assess the effect of robot penetration on household income inequality, we first evaluate their impact on key labor market channels: wages and employment. The complementarity between robots and different types of human tasks likely led to both wage and employment *gains* and *losses* for different workers. The net effect on the labor income distribution is ambiguous, especially across countries differing in industrial and occupational structures. We adopt the approach proposed by Acemoglu and Restrepo (2022) to estimate the effects of automation on labor market outcomes. These effects are identified by regressing labor market outcomes of demographic groups against changes in their exposure to automation-driven task displacement shocks. We define 30 demographic groups in each country based on workers' age, gender and education. We use large harmonized linked employer-employee data from the EU Structure of Earnings Survey and supplement it with other sources. Since adopting robots may be endogenous to labor demand, we use an instrumental variable approach. We exploit plausibly exogenous variation in the penetration of robots, based on trends in robot adoption in five European countries outside of our sample, interacted with initial employment structures of demographic groups in the sample. In other words, our instrument measures the exposure to penetration of robots for demographic groups if industries in which a demographic group specializes would imitate overall trends in robot adoption.

We show that in Western Europe, similarly to the U.S. (Acemoglu and Restrepo, 2022), robot penetration significantly reduced wages and employment rates between 2006 and 2018. We find, however, that despite a significant effect on labor market outcomes, automation did not affect total household disposable incomes in Western Europe. The negative earnings and employment effects were mitigated by risk-sharing within households (earnings losses

of workers affected by rising robot penetration were cushioned by stable or rising earnings of other household members) and redistribution (taxes and benefits). By contrast, we find insignificant effects of robot penetration on wages and employment in Eastern Europe. These different impacts are consistent with international differences in labor costs. The price of robot technology is uniform across countries, so the substitution of workers with robots is more likely in countries with higher labor costs.³ Indeed, Bachmann et al. (2022) and de Vries et al. (2020) also found that the labor market effects of robots are more benign in European countries with lower labor costs.

In the second part of the paper, we investigate the distributional effects of automation and the role of household formation and redistributive policies in particular countries in our sample. The estimated wage and employment effects of automation serve as input to the EUROMOD microsimulation model. Specifically, we simulate a counterfactual distribution of disposable household income for 2018. We assume ‘undoing’ the change in employment and wages that we attribute to increased robot penetration since 2006 (based on econometric results discussed above). Changes in wages and employment are directly modelled in individual-level micro-data to simulate changes in pre-tax earnings. We then use the EUROMOD tax-benefit calculator to assess what these changes in pre-tax earnings imply for household disposable income after we allow for compensation through benefits and taxation. This follows a decomposition framework formalised by Bargain and Callan (2010). Similar methods have been used in the literature about the drivers of income inequality to estimate the contribution of tax-benefit policy (Černiauskas et al., 2022; Paulus and Tasseva, 2020), of employment and wage changes (Li, La, and Sologon, 2021; Doorley, Callan, and Savage, 2021) and of demographic change (Dolls, Doorley, et al., 2019) to changes in income inequality in Europe. However, no study so far has looked at the contribution of robots – as a specific driver of wage and employment changes to income inequality in Europe.

We find that the rising penetration of industrial robots had a positive but tiny contribution to income inequality in European countries. In most countries, this contribution amounts to less than 1 percent of the baseline level of income inequality in 2006, as measured with the Gini index of equivalised household income.⁴ Hence, the significant effects of robot adoption on labor market outcomes do not appear to translate into substantial changes in income inequality in Europe. There are two reasons for this. First, the labor market effects are economically small, even close to zero for most of the demographic groups. Specifically, in Western Europe, statistically significant negative earnings effects were partly cushioned by stable or increasing earnings of other household members. In Eastern Europe, the income effects of robot penetration were close to zero, as small positive wage effects were offset by small negative employment effects.

³In Eastern Europe, multinational firms that aim to synchronise production standards across plants and value chains drive robot adoption. Consequently, robot penetration in Eastern Europe is higher than expected based on only labor costs (Cséfalvay, 2020).

⁴Unless otherwise stated, disposable household income is equivalised in the remainder of the paper.

Second, European countries' tax and benefit systems appear well-prepared to cushion such shocks. It is especially the case in Western countries. Moreover, benefits played a larger role in cushioning robot-driven labor market shocks than taxes. The benefit systems reduced the effect of automation on income inequality particularly strongly in Germany, Belgium, and Sweden. At the same time, welfare states in Eastern European countries were less efficient in cushioning automation-driven shocks. In most Eastern countries, the targeting of benefits widened inequality. This means that demographic groups that benefited from automation-driven shocks received more transfers, while groups that suffered from these shocks - received less. However, as the economic size of these shocks in Eastern countries was small, the consequences for household income inequality were minimal. To sum up, while inequality increased in many European countries between 2006 and 2018, it was not because of rising robot penetration, but due to other market income changes or shifts in tax-benefit systems unrelated to automation.

Overall, we make two key contributions. First, we provide (causal) evidence of the medium-term effects of the penetration of robots on wages and employment in a cross-country setting of European countries. These effects may be different from those estimated by Acemoglu and Restrepo (2022) for the U.S. due to large differences in labor market institutions, including minimum wages, collective bargaining, and employment protection. Other studies showed that the net effect of robots and other routine-replacing technologies on employment in Europe has been moderately positive (Bachmann et al., 2022; Dauth et al., 2021; Gregory, Salomons, and Zierahn, 2021). At the same time, robots widened the gender pay gap in Europe (Aksoy, Özcan, and Philipp, 2021). We show that in the most developed European economies, automation had negative medium-term effects on employment and wages. However, in the less developed European countries, it had more benign consequences.

Our second contribution is to quantify how these automation-driven shocks to wages and employment have contributed to changes in household income inequality in European countries. To our knowledge, it is the first evaluation of how robots have affected household income inequality in Europe over time. We separately identify the effect of automation-driven wage changes and employment changes on income inequality in each European country in our sample. We also show how the household formation and the tax-benefit system affect the transmission of the associated market income change into disposable income inequality.

The paper is organised as follows. In section 2 we present our data and measurements. In section 3 we outline our empirical strategy. In section 4 we present and discuss our results, and in section 5 we summarise and conclude.

2 Data and measurement

2.1 Data sources and definitions

Our sources of worker-level data are the European Union Structure of Earnings Survey (EU-SES), the EU Labour Force Survey (EU-LFS), and the EU Survey of Income and Living Conditions (EU-SILC). The EU-LFS is the main cross-country survey in the EU that provides data on employment outcomes, covering all workers. However, it doesn't include data on wages. The EU-SES is the most comprehensive, cross-country survey of wages in the EU. It provides representative and harmonised information on employees in firms with at least 10 workers. Finally, the EU-SILC is the main cross-country survey in the EU that measures incomes, both market and non-market, before and after taxation, at individual and household level.

Our sample includes the following 14 countries, allocated to groups: Belgium, France, Germany, Netherlands, Sweden (Western European countries), Bulgaria, Czechia, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, and Slovakia (Eastern European countries).⁵ We cover the period between 2006 and 2018, a period of noticeable technology adoption in many countries.⁶

Our unit of analysis is a demographic group. For each country, we define 30 demographic groups defined by gender (men and women), education (basic, secondary, tertiary), and age (10-year age groups). We use the worker-level EU-SES data to calculate average real hourly wages by demographic group and country in 2006 and 2018. Then, we calculate the log change in these average hourly wages for workers in a given group between 2006–2018.⁷ We use the EU-LFS to calculate employment rates by demographic group and country in 2006 and 2018, and take their difference. Finally, we use the EUROMOD linked to EU-SILC data to simulate the average individual and equivalised household income by demographic group and country in 2006 and 2018, and their log difference.

We also use the EU-SES to calculate shares of workers in routine jobs by demographic group and country. We apply the typology of Lewandowski et al. (2020), based on the Occupational Information Network (O*NET) data, to define routine occupations at the 2-digit level of the International Standard Classification of Occupations (ISCO).

We use adjusted penetration of robots as a measure of automation following Acemoglu and Restrepo (2020). The data on robots come from the International Federation of Robotics

⁵The surveys we use are collected in all European Union member states, but our sample includes 14 countries as other data discussed below are unavailable for certain countries.

⁶The EU-SES has been conducted every four years since 2002. However, the 2002 data for Estonia, Latvia, and Hungary are incomplete, so we study the 2006–2018 period.

⁷We calculate gross hourly wages by dividing gross monthly earnings for the reference month by the number of hours paid during the reference month. Gross monthly earnings include earnings related to overtime, special payments for shift work, compulsory social contribution, and taxes. They do not include irregular, ad hoc and exceptional bonuses and other payments that do not feature every pay period.

(IFR), which provides annual information covering the current stock and the deliveries of industrial robots across countries, by industry and by application. We construct the measure of penetration of robots by country and industry:

$$(1) \quad APR_{i,c} = \frac{M_{i,c,2018} - M_{i,c,2006}}{L_{i,c,2006}} - \frac{Y_{i,c,2018} - Y_{i,c,2006}}{Y_{i,c,2006}} \cdot \frac{M_{i,c,2006}}{L_{i,c,2006}}$$

where $M_{i,c,t}$ represents the number of robots in industry i in country c in year t (current stock), $L_{i,c,2006}$ represents the baseline employment level in industry i and country c , and $Y_{i,c,t}$ represents real output of sector i in country c in year t .

Then, following Acemoglu and Restrepo (2022), for each demographic group g and country c , we construct the following direct measure of task displacement due to penetration of robots:

$$(2) \quad TDA_{g,c} = \sum_{i \in I} \omega_{g,c}^i \cdot (\omega_{g,i,c}^R / \omega_{i,c}^R) \cdot APR_{i,c}$$

the measure comprises of three terms:

- a group's exposure to different industries, $\omega_{g,c}^i$, which is given by the share of wages earned by workers of a group g in industry i in country c .
- $\omega_{g,i,c}^R / \omega_{i,c}^R$ which captures the relative specialization of a group g in industry i 's routine jobs, where displacement takes place.
- $APR_{i,c}$, adjusted penetration of robots in industry i in country c .

Similarly, we construct industry shifters as weighted averages of changes in sectors' value added using the shares of various sectors in a demographic group's employment structure as weights. In the analysis, we use logs of $TDA_{g,c}$ to account for skewed distribution of the variable.⁸

2.2 Descriptive statistics

Table 1 presents the means of variables used to assign workers into socio-demographic groups and those used in regressions. We report these averages by region of Europe. The demographic composition of workers is quite similar across regions. At the same time, average changes in real hourly wages varied substantially between the regions. On average, workers in Western Europe observed zero real hourly wage growth. By contrast, workers in Eastern Europe experienced a remarkable real wage growth of 40 log points. Disposable incomes (equalized household incomes after tax and transfers) increased by 24 log points

⁸Few groups experience negative displacement so we take logs of $TDA_{g,c}$ after adding one.

in Western Europe and 95 log points in Eastern Europe. In Eastern Europe, workers were exposed to a 25 log points increase in real value added. In Western Europe, the growth of value added was twice as low as in Eastern Europe. Employment rates slightly increased in both regions.

On average, the penetration of robots, our measure of automation, was similar in Western and Eastern Europe. The average relative exposure to routine tasks was equal to zero in all countries which reflects the construction of this measure. The initial manufacturing employment shares were similar in both regions, as manufacturing accounted for around 25 percent of employment in Europe.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics by region

	Western Europe	Eastern Europe
Gender: woman	0.46	0.49
Gender: man	0.54	0.51
Basic education	0.18	0.13
Secondary education	0.52	0.58
Tertiary education	0.29	0.29
Age: 20-29	0.19	0.19
Age: 30-39	0.26	0.27
Age: 40-49	0.29	0.27
Age: 50-59	0.22	0.22
Age: 60+	0.05	0.05
Log wage growth	0.00	0.38
Log income growth	0.24	0.95
Employment rate change	0.02	0.05
Automation	0.91	0.84
Routine tasks	1.00	1.00
Industry shifters	0.12	0.23
Manufacturing share	0.23	0.26
Observations	150	270

Notes: This table presents weighted means of selected variables. We weigh observations by their within-country employment shares. The sources and description of the variables can be found in Table A.1. Detailed descriptive statistics for all variables for the whole sample are presented in Table A.2.

Descriptively, we see that the relationship between changes in exposure to robots and real wage growth varies substantially between regions (Figure 2) - it is negative in Western, but positive in Eastern Europe.

Figure 2. Automation and wage growth in Europe

Notes: Figures show relationship between adjusted penetration of robots and real hourly wages (residualized after controlling for country fixed effects) for demographic groups in 14 countries. Panel A plots the relationship for Western European countries (Belgium, France, Germany, Netherlands, Sweden). Panel B plots the relationship for Eastern European countries (Bulgaria, Czechia, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Slovakia). Marker sizes indicate the within-country employment shares of demographic groups.

Data: EU-SES.

3 Empirical Strategy

Our analysis is divided into three steps (Figure 3). First, we estimate the impact of automation on wages and employment rates of demographic groups following the methodology of Acemoglu and Restrepo (2022). Second, we use the estimated coefficients to create counterfactual wages and employment rates that would be recorded in 2018 if robot penetration remained at the 2006 level in each country. Third, we use these counterfactual effects as inputs for micro-simulation using the EUROMOD microsimulation model to investigate the effects on household incomes.

Figure 3. Research design

Source: own elaboration.

Effects of automation on wages and employment rates

We estimate the following equation to investigate the impact of automation on wages:

$$(3) \quad \Delta \ln W_{g,c} = \beta TDA_{g,c} + \kappa X_{g,c} + \alpha_{edu(g,c)} + \gamma_{gender(g,c)} + \eta_{country(g,c)} + \nu_{g,c}$$

where $\Delta \ln W_{g,c}$ denotes the log change in real hourly wages for workers in a demographic group g in the country c between 2006 and 2018. The coefficient of interest is β , which may be interpreted as a change in wages due to a one percent increase in exposure to automation. We control for country fixed effects, $\eta_{country(g,c)}$, gender and education fixed effects ($\gamma_{gender(g,c)}$ and $\alpha_{edu(g,c)}$), and additional control variables ($X_{g,c}$): exposure to manufacturing, relative specialization in routine tasks, and industry shifters. While industry shifters absorb labour demand changes coming from the expansion of industries in which a demographic group specializes, the group-specific shifters account for demand factors related to changing wage premia associated with gender, education, and working in manufacturing. Regressions are weighted by the share of each group in each country's employment, and standard errors are robust to heteroskedasticity.

As the relationship between changes in exposure to robots and real wage growth appears to vary between regions (Figure 2), we account for the interactions of the exposure to robots with

region fixed effects (Western and Eastern Europe), and we estimate the following equation:

$$(4) \quad \begin{aligned} \Delta \ln W_{g,c} = & \beta^{West} TDA_{g,c} \times West_{g,c} \\ & + \beta^{East} TDA_{g,c} \times East_{g,c} \\ & + \kappa X_{g,c} + \alpha_{edu(g,c)} + \gamma_{gender(g,c)} + \eta_{country(g,c)} + \nu_{g,c} \end{aligned}$$

We use the same approach for employment rates, the only difference is that we use differences in employment rates rather than log differences as in the case of wages.

The OLS estimation of equation (4) may lead to biased estimates because the robot adoption in industry i in country c may be determined by changes in unobservable factors that simultaneously affect labor demand in this industry. Hence, we use the approach of Acemoglu and Restrepo (2020) and instrument the penetration of robots in industry i by an average penetration in this industry among five European countries, e to identify the component of robot penetration driven by changes in technology:

$$(5) \quad APR_i^{IV} = \frac{1}{5} \sum_{e=1}^5 \left[\frac{M_{i,e,2018} - M_{i,e,2006}}{L_{i,e,2006}} - \frac{Y_{i,e,2018} - Y_{i,e,2006}}{Y_{i,e,2006}} \cdot \frac{M_{i,e,2006}}{L_{i,e,2006}} \right]$$

In the first stage of the IV estimation, we again allow the relationship between our instrument and the penetration of robots to vary depending on the region. The original instrument in Acemoglu and Restrepo (2020) comprised Denmark, Finland, France, Italy, and Sweden. Since two of these countries are included in our sample (France, and Sweden), we must modify the original instrument. In addition, we decided to exclude Italy from the instrument, as it is the only major European economy that experienced a decline in exposure to robots between 2006 and 2018. Our instrument comprises Austria, Denmark, Finland, Slovenia, and the UK.⁹ In robustness tests, we also present the results using the instrument comprising countries selected originally by Acemoglu and Restrepo (2020).

Microsimulation of effects on disposable income inequality

The last stage of analysis consists in drawing implications of automation for disposable household income inequality. We do so by ‘injecting’ our estimated wage and employment effects of automation into a tax-benefit microsimulation model and representative data on household incomes. We thereby assess how much automation-induced change in wages and employment can account for the change in household income inequality observed in European countries between 2008 and 2016.

We use EUROMOD for this analysis. EUROMOD is a static tax-benefit calculator for the EU countries, which allows for a comparative analysis of tax-benefit systems and their impact on

⁹These countries are not included in our analysis because the SES data is unavailable for these countries.

income distribution in a consistent way through a common framework (Sutherland and Figari, 2013). Based on a representative household sample of national populations with information about their socio-demographic and labor market characteristics as well as market incomes (earnings, but also capital income), EUROMOD simulates disposable income for households by applying (existing or counterfactual) tax-benefit rules.

The EUROMOD input-data are mainly based on the EU-SILC data released by Eurostat. We use version I4.0 of EUROMOD with input datasets based primarily on the SILC 2006 and 2018 waves.

We are interested in the implications of automation-induced changes in wage and employment on the distribution of *household disposable income*, equivalised to account for household size and composition by using the modified OECD equivalence scale. Disposable income, as widely used to measure poverty and inequality, is defined as all household incomes net of taxes and social contributions and after the receipt of all types of cash benefits. Household *market income* (or original income) refers to the total amount of labor income (excluding employer social insurance contributions), capital income, private pensions and private transfers, i.e. income before taxes and benefits. Automation in our simulation is going to modify hourly wages and/or employment probabilities of salaried workers. This is going to be transmitted through to disposable incomes via modification of individual annual labour incomes. How much it impacts disposable income will depend on other income sources at the level of households and on taxes and benefits.

To assess the impact of wage changes and its contribution to the evolution of income inequality between 2006 and 2018, we use and extend the framework outlined by Bargain and Callan (2010). Denote $\mathbf{Y} := (X, Y^L, Z)$ a $N \times k$ matrix with, for each of N households, $k - 2$ socio-demographic characteristics (X , including gender, education and age of all household members), labour income (Y^L), and other market incomes (Z). Let $d(\cdot, p)$ denote a ‘tax-benefit function’ which calculates household disposable income on the basis of household characteristics, pre-tax incomes, and a set of tax-benefit policy rules and parameters. p denotes nominal values of monetary tax-benefit parameters (e.g., tax brackets, benefit amounts, eligibility thresholds, etc.). So, $y^d = d(\mathbf{Y}, p)$ is a $N \times 1$ vector of final disposable incomes implied by the tax-benefit system for a population with market incomes and characteristics given by \mathbf{Y} . Income inequality in disposable income is denoted $I[y^d]$ where $I : R^N \mapsto [0, 1]$ is a summary inequality index such as the Gini coefficient.

Introducing subscripts for time, we write inequality in year t as $I[d_t((X_t, Y_t^L, Z_t), p_t)]$. The total change in a given distributional index between two time periods, $t = 0$ (2006) and $t = 1$ (2018), can then be written as

$$(6) \quad \Delta I = I[d_1((X_1, Y_1^L, Z_1), p_1)] - I[d_0((X_0, Y_0^L, Z_0), p_0)]$$

A full decomposition exercise is then based on the construction of various counterfactual distributions. For example, we can define inequality in the distribution of disposable income for the population and labour incomes of year k , under the tax-benefit structure of year i and the tax-benefit nominal parameters of year j as $I [(d_i((X_k, Y_k^L, Z_k), p_j)]$ and compare such counterfactual inequality index to a reference, baseline inequality. Gradually introducing changes in various terms from the baseline period 0 to their value in 1 and adding up the marginal changes in simulated inequality coefficients leads to a decomposition of the total inequality change.

In the present analysis however, we are not after complete decomposition results. We are primarily interested in assessing the *marginal* change in the Gini coefficient induced by automation-induced employment changes and automation-induced wage changes, separately from the effect of other, simultaneous changes in wages, employment, population characteristics and tax-benefit policy. To do so, we construct the following simulated distributions. The automation-induced employment change effect is obtained by constructing

$$\Delta^{AE}I = I [d_1((X_1, Y_1^L, Z_1), p_1)] - I [d_1((\tilde{X}_1, Y_1^L, Z_1), p_1)]$$

where \tilde{X}_1 is the period 1 data reweighted such that employment probabilities by socio-demographic groups (by education, gender and age cells) map the employment probabilities that would have been expected in 2018 in the absence of automation effects. The automation-induced wage effect is obtained as

$$\Delta^{AW}I = I [d_1((X_1, Y_1^L, Z_1), p_1)] - I [d_1((X_1, \tilde{Y}_1^L, Z_1), p_1)]$$

where \tilde{Y}_1^L is period 1 wages of employed individuals scaled down by the automation-induced predicted wage growth by socio-demographic group between period 0 and 1

$$(7) \quad \tilde{Y}_1^L = \text{diag}(dw(X_0))Y_1^L$$

where $dw(X_0)$ is the vector automation-induced relative change in wage for the year 0 population (X_0 includes gender, education, age characteristics). The contribution of the combination between wage and employment is obtained by combining counterfactuals:

$$\Delta^{AWE}I = I [d_1((\tilde{X}_1, \tilde{Y}_1^L, Z_1), p_1)] - I [d_1((X_1, Y_1^L, Z_1), p_1)].$$

The three terms Δ^{AE} , Δ^{AW} and Δ^{AWE} capture the effect of automation that we are primarily interested in (holding everything else constant in the base year 1—other incomes, individual characteristics, and tax-benefit policies). The estimates of the terms can be interpreted as the marginal change in the Gini coefficient that we would observe relative to 2018 if we apply a time-machine that undoes the effect of automation-induced employment and/or wage change since 2006.

Note that to probe into the role of different tax-benefit systems in cushioning automation-induced earnings changes (through employment and wages), we calculate Gini coefficients for both disposable and market incomes under different tax-benefit rules. The latter is obtained from household pre-tax and pre-transfer incomes without application of the $d(\cdot, p)$ tax-benefit function. In counterfactual scenarios, wages and employment are adjusted for automation and the resulting market incomes are simply added across sources and household members. Accordingly, the double differences between pre-tax and post-tax distributions, with and without neutralization of automation-induced changes reflect how much taxes and benefits absorbed the automation impacts on disposable incomes.

Finally, we also report a separate set of marginal effects based on the automation-induced wage and employment changes observed in Germany: relative wage change and employment probabilities by education, gender and age cells calculated for Germany are ‘injected’ in each of the other countries’ models. This is obtained as above except that the modified \tilde{X}_1^L and \tilde{Y}_1^L are obtained from the OLS results for Germany. These results help assess how much differences across countries in the impact of automation are due to differences in the size and nature of the automation shock versus to differences in how automation combines with existing socio-demographic structure, other income sources and taxes and benefits.

4 Results

We start with econometric results - the estimated effect of robot exposure on wages, employment rates, and incomes - followed by the microsimulation results.

The wage effects of robot exposure

We start with a discussion of the OLS estimates of the effects of robot exposure on wage growth in Europe. The size and the direction of these effects differ across European countries (Table 2). The effects of a one percent increase in the adjusted penetration of robots range from strongly negative effects in Western Europe to moderately positive estimates in Eastern Europe. As described above, these estimates may be biased. Therefore, we use the instrumental variable approach and obtain very similar results (see Table 2). In Western Europe, we find a significant negative effect of automation: a one percent increase in the penetration of robots leads to a decline in real wages by almost 13%. In Eastern Europe, the effects of automation on wages are statistically insignificant and small.

The estimated effects are robust to changes in specification and adding more controls. Our preferred specification is shown in Column 5 of Table 2. It includes controls for group-specific shifters (gender and education fixed effects as well as demographic groups’ exposures to

Table 2. Automation and changes in real hourly wages, 2006-2018

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
	OLS	OLS	OLS	OLS	OLS
Automation*Western Europe	-0.089*** (0.017)	-0.098*** (0.017)	-0.113*** (0.017)	-0.126*** (0.018)	-0.128*** (0.017)
Automation*Eastern Europe	0.098*** (0.015)	0.074*** (0.016)	0.059*** (0.017)	0.044** (0.019)	0.036** (0.018)
	2SLS	2SLS	2SLS	2SLS	2SLS
Automation*Western Europe	-0.064*** (0.020)	-0.073*** (0.020)	-0.096*** (0.022)	-0.120*** (0.025)	-0.125*** (0.024)
Automation*Eastern Europe	0.145*** (0.023)	0.110*** (0.026)	0.079*** (0.025)	0.047 (0.030)	0.039 (0.030)
Country FE	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Manufacturing share	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Gender	no	yes	yes	yes	yes
Education	no	no	yes	yes	yes
Routine tasks	no	no	no	yes	yes
Industry shifters	no	no	no	no	yes
F-statistic first stage	148.66	131.46	96.16	64.96	65.89
Mean of outcome	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
Mean of automation	0.82	0.82	0.82	0.82	0.82
Observations	420	420	420	420	420

Notes: Table shows estimates of the relationship between task displacement due to automation and the change in log wages across 30 demographic groups in 14 European countries. The upper panel shows the OLS estimates and the bottom panel shows the IV estimates. The dependent variable is the change in log wages for each group from 2006 to 2018. The instrument is the average robot penetration in 5 European countries not included in the sample. All regressions are weighted by the group's share of the country's employment. Column 4 shows our baseline estimates. Robust standard errors are reported. Table B.1 shows the first-stage results.

Data: EU-SES. * p<.10; ** p<.05; *** p<.01

manufacturing), groups' relative specialization in routine tasks, and industry shifters (groups' exposures to changes in value added of sectors they specialize in).

In further robustness checks, we show that the results remain largely unchanged when we control for groups' specialization in routine jobs and exposure to industry labour share decline, offshoring, Chinese imports penetration, minimum wage, and population changes (Table B.2 in Appendix B).

The employment effects of robot exposure

Next, we discuss the estimates of the impact of automation on employment. Again, we find important heterogeneity between the country groups. In Western Europe, the effect of robot adoption had a significant, negative effect on employment rates (Table 3). Combined with

negative wage effects of robot adoption (Table 2), our estimates suggest a negative effects of automation on labour market outcomes and labour income in Western European countries. Finally, in Eastern European countries we find no significant effect of robot adoption on employment rates (Table 3), similar to insignificant effect on wages in our preferred specification (Column 5 of Table 2)

Table 3. Automation and changes in employment rates, 2006-2018

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
	2SLS	2SLS	2SLS	2SLS	2SLS
Automation*Western Europe	-0.039** (0.017)	-0.041** (0.017)	-0.097*** (0.020)	-0.084*** (0.024)	-0.085*** (0.024)
Automation*Eastern Europe	0.044** (0.019)	0.038* (0.021)	-0.045* (0.025)	-0.027 (0.029)	-0.029 (0.029)
Country FE	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Manufacturing share	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Gender	no	yes	yes	yes	yes
Education	no	no	yes	yes	yes
Routine tasks	no	no	no	yes	yes
Industry shifters	no	no	no	no	yes
F-statistic first stage	148.66	131.46	96.16	64.96	65.89
Mean of outcome	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
Mean of automation	2.41	2.41	2.41	2.41	2.41
Observations	420	420	420	420	420

Notes: Table shows estimates of the relationship between task displacement due to automation and the change in employment rates across 30 demographic groups in 14 European countries. The dependent variable is the change in employment rates for each group from 2006 to 2018. The instrument is the average robot penetration in 5 European countries not included in the sample. Robust standard errors are reported.

Data: EU-SES. * p<.10; ** p<.05; *** p<.01

The income effects of robot exposure

Table 4 summarizes the reduced-form 2SLS estimates of the effects of automation on hourly wages, individual market income, household market income, and household total disposable income. This exercise demonstrates how the automation shock to employment and wages is translated into household disposable income. We focus on our preferred specification with the most controls.

In Western Europe, the negative effect of automation on wages translate into even larger negative effects on individual monthly earnings. This is due to the fact that automation also had a strong, negative impact on employment (Table 3). Moving from individual to household market income, equalised to account for household composition, the negative effect of automation is halved thanks to risk sharing within households. Moving from equalised market income to equalised disposable income - i.e. accounting for the tax and welfare system -

completely mitigates the negative effect of automation. This indicates that, after some of the automation shock has been diluted through household members sharing its consequences, redistribution by the tax and welfare system cushions the remaining automation shock.

In Eastern Europe, we estimate a smaller negative effect of automation on individual market income. This translates into a small positive effect of automation on both household equivalised market and disposable income, suggesting that household formation cushions any negative income effects of automation in Eastern Europe. However, as none of the effects are precisely estimated, it is impossible to draw firm conclusions for this region.

Table 4. Automation and changes in income, 2006-2018

	(1) Hourly wage 2 SLS	(2) Ind. market income 2 SLS	(3) HH market income 2 SLS	(4) HH disposable income 2 SLS
Automation*Western Europe	-0.125*** (0.024)	-0.313*** (0.105)	-0.168** (0.069)	-0.008 (0.040)
Automation*Eastern Europe	0.039 (0.030)	-0.038 (0.096)	0.051 (0.061)	0.079* (0.041)
Country FE	yes	yes	yes	yes
Manufacturing share	yes	yes	yes	yes
Gender	yes	yes	yes	yes
Education	yes	yes	yes	yes
Routine tasks	yes	yes	yes	yes
Industry shifters	yes	yes	yes	yes
F-statistic first stage	65.89	63.96	63.96	63.96
Mean of outcome	0.25	0.76	0.76	0.69
Mean of automation	2.41	2.41	2.41	2.41
Observations	420	330	330	330

Notes: Table shows estimates of the relationship between automation (penetration of robots) and measures of income across 30 demographic groups in 14 European countries. In column 1, the dependent variable is the change in log wages for each group from 2006 to 2018. In column 2, the dependent variable is the change in log equivalised individual market income for each group from 2006 to 2018. In column 3, the dependent variable is the log equivalised household market income change for each group from 2006 to 2018. In column 4, the dependent variable is the log household total disposable income change for each group from 2006 to 2018. The instrument is the average robot penetration in 5 European countries not included in the sample. All regressions are weighted by the group's share of the country's employment. Robust standard errors are reported.

Data: EU-SES. * p<.10; ** p<.05; *** p<.01

To provide a comparison to the U.S., we first replicate the results of Acemoglu and Restrepo (2022), and then estimate reduced-form effects of penetration of robots on changes in individual market income, average household market income, and household income after taxes and transfers. We find that in the U.S., the negative earnings effects at the worker level are further exacerbated at the household level (Table B.4 in Appendix B). This suggests that the correlation of automation-driven shocks within households is larger in the U.S. than in the European countries.¹⁰ Finally, we show that, in the U.S., the negative effect of automation on market incomes is passed through to disposable income with just one-third absorbed by

¹⁰This could perhaps result from a higher prevalence of assortative mating in the U.S. than in Europe.

the tax and transfer system. This suggests that U.S. taxes and transfers in the U.S. have not been as effective in mitigating the adverse effects of automation as in Western Europe.

Distribution of wage and employment changes due to automation

Next, we describe the distribution of the wage and employment changes attributed to differences in robot exposure between 2006 and 2018. These changes are inputs for the microsimulation analysis. We calculate them by multiplying the estimated parameters β by the value of task displacement shock recorded for each demographic group in particular countries that belong to a given country group.

We find a substantial dispersion of the estimated contributions of automation to wage changes - they range from -25 to 20 log points (Figure 4). The dispersion of estimated contributions to employment rate changes is much smaller - the effects range from -15 pp. to 0, with the mass being concentrated in 0 (Figure 5).

Figure 4. Distribution of wage changes due to automation

Notes: Figure shows the distribution of wage changes due to automation for demographic groups. Wage changes due to automation are calculated by multiplying the group's increase in the exposure to automation by the wage effects of automation from the equation 4. We plot the distribution for the restricted sample of groups representing at least 1% of the countries' employment.

Data: EU-SES.

Figure 5. Distribution of employment rate changes due to automation

Notes: Figure shows the distribution of employment rate changes due to automation for demographic groups. Employment changes due to automation are calculated by multiplying the group's increase in the exposure to automation by the employment effects of automation. We plot the distribution for the restricted sample of groups representing at least 1% of the countries' employment.
Data: EU-SES.

We also find some systematic differences between demographic groups (results are shown in Appendix B). First, in absolute terms, wage changes due to automation are smaller for women than for men (Figure B.1), and employment changes are more concentrated in 0 among women than among men (Figure B.6). Second, the higher the education level attained by workers, the more concentrated the distribution of wage and employment changes due to automation (Figures B.3e and B.8e). The largest dispersion of wage and employment effects attributed to robot exposure is among workers with primary education levels. In particular, in Western Europe, workers with primary education experienced the largest wage declines. The negative employment effects were much more common among workers with primary education levels than among workers with secondary or tertiary education levels. Third, the distribution of wage and employment changes attributed to automation is similar across age groups (Figures B.3- B.8).

The distribution of the wage changes due to automation for each country is presented in Figures B.4 and B.5. We find large wage gains in two Eastern European countries (Czechia and Slovakia). By contrast, workers in Germany, Netherlands, and Sweden experienced large wage declines due to automation. In the remaining countries (Bulgaria, Estonia, France, Hungary, Lithuania, Latvia, Poland, Romania, and Sweden), wage changes attributed to automation were very small.

(a) Western Europe

(b) Eastern Europe

Figure 6. Wage changes due to automation across the wage distribution

Notes: Figures show the average wage changes due to automation for percentiles of the wage distribution. Wage changes due to automation are calculated by multiplying the group's increase in the exposure to automation by the wage effects of automation from the equation 4. Panel A plots the relationship for Western European countries (Belgium, France, Germany, Netherlands, and Sweden). Panel B plots the relationship for Eastern European countries (Bulgaria, Czechia, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, and Slovakia). Data: EU-SES.

Figure 6 shows wage changes due to automation for percentiles of the wage distribution. The exposure to automation was strongest for low-wage workers. Hence, the largest wage declines due to automation in Western Europe were recorded for demographic groups with wages below the country average. The opposite relationship was observed in Eastern Europe.

The overall EU wage inequality decreased due to automation. Even though the negatively affected groups in Western Europe were concentrated at the bottom of their countries' wage distributions, their initial wage levels were still above the EU average (Figure B.11). By contrast, lower-wage economies of Eastern Europe experienced small wage increases due to automation.

The contribution of automation to household income inequality

Next, we present and discuss the results of counterfactual simulations of income distribution from the EUROMOD microsimulation model. We use the estimated contributions of robot exposure to changes in demographic groups' wages and employment rates between 2006 and 2018 as inputs for the microsimulation model. The results show how much of the change in income inequality in particular countries can be attributed to automation.

There is much variation in how income inequality, as measured by the Gini Index, has evolved in European countries between 2006 and 2018 (Figure 7). In some countries (Hungary, Bulgaria, Lithuania and Sweden) income inequality increased substantially, with the Gini Index increasing by more than 10 percent. In others (Slovakia, Poland and Estonia), income inequality declined over the same period.

Figure 8 focuses on the contribution of automation to the overall change in income inequality by country. It is split into the contributions of (i) automation-related wage changes (ii) automation-induced employment changes and (iii) the interaction between these two using the methods described in Section 3.

Automation-induced wage changes - which we estimate to be negative in Western Europe and positive or zero in Eastern Europe - have had a small effect on income inequality in most countries studied over this period. This is visible in Figure 7, but also in Figure 8, which shows only automation related changes in income inequality. Typically, automation-driven wage changes slightly decreased income inequality in Western European countries and slightly increased income inequality in Eastern European countries. Our results show the largest positive contributions in Czechia (+0.9 percent) and Bulgaria (+0.4 per cent) and the largest negative contributions in Germany (-2.6 per cent) and Belgium (-2.9 per cent). Most other changes represent less than 1 per cent of the 2006 value of the Gini Index.

Automation-driven employment changes - which we estimate to be negative in Western Europe and negative or zero in Eastern Europe - have modestly widened inequality in most countries. The size of the employment contribution is roughly comparable to the size of the wage

contribution (8, although in the case of Western European countries, it goes in the opposite direction to the wage contribution. The largest effects are observed in Sweden, Germany and Belgium (+ 0.7, + 1 and 1.3 percent, respectively). Other countries experienced smaller income inequality increases or no increase due to automation-driven employment changes.

We also quantify the contribution of the interaction between the wage and employment effects. In most countries, the size of these interactions is tiny.

The wage, employment and interaction effects sum to give the overall contribution of automation to household inequality between 2006 and 2018. In most countries, it is positive but small - less than 1 percent of the baseline level of the Gini index in 2006 (Figure 7-8). Two Western Europe exceptions are Germany and Belgium where automation has decreased income inequality by -1 and -0.9 per cent respectively. In Eastern Europe, the Czech Republic stands out with automation increasing income inequality by 1.3 per cent.

Compared to the overall change in household income inequality in each country, the marginal effect of automation - the sum of the induced wage and employment effects and their interaction - is very small. It exceeds 1 percent of the the baseline level of the Gini index only in Czechia. This suggests that other changes in market income and the tax-benefit systems played a much larger role than robot adoption in the evolution of income inequality in European countries between 2006-2018.

Figure 7. Effect of automation on inequality in disposable household income: a decomposition analysis

Notes: The figure shows the total change in the Gini Index between 2006 and 2018 as well as the terms of the decomposition of the change in household income inequality (automation-induced wage effect, automation-induced employment effect, their interaction and the total automation effect). Data: EUROMOD, EU-SILC.

Figure 8. Effect of automation on inequality in disposable household income

Notes: The figure shows the terms of the decomposition of the change in household income inequality (automation-induced wage effect, automation-induced employment effect, their interaction and the total automation effect). Data: EUROMOD, EU-SILC.

The cushioning effect of the tax-benefit system: taxes versus benefits

Despite evidence from Figure 6 that automation increased wage inequality in Western Europe, we show that automation driven wage changes are inequality decreasing when we examine equivalised disposable income. This suggests an important role for either household formation or tax and transfer systems (or both) in mitigating or cushioning this wage inequality.

To tease this out, we next estimate the automation-induced change in the Gini Index for different income concepts. Comparing the change in the Gini Index of market income at the individual level to that of equivalised market income at the household level shows the effect of household formation on the change in income inequality. Plotting the change in the Gini Index of market income at the household level, of gross income (market income plus welfare) and of net income (market income minus tax) also allows us to show how the automation-induced change in income inequality of market income is cushioned by the tax and welfare systems separately as market income is transformed into disposable income.

Figure 9 shows the Gini Index (i) of individual level market income of those aged 20-65 **check**, (ii) of equivalised household market income and (iii) of equivalised household disposable income (as Figures 8 does) Comparing (i) to (ii) illustrates the effect of household formation on the transmission of the automation shock while comparing (ii) to (iii) shows the cushioning

effect of taxes and benefits. For many countries, these effects are very small, indicating that income sharing within households and the tax-benefit system either do little to cushion the automation-driven market income shock or that they have little work to do given the small magnitude of the shock.

In Western European and some Eastern European countries, automation increases inequality of individual level market income. This is in line with earlier descriptive evidence on the effects of automation on wage inequality. The corresponding increase in market income inequality at the household level is typically smaller, indicating that household formation plays some role in mitigating the automation shock. Only in Sweden does household formation slightly amplify the effect of automation induced income inequality changes. In Western European countries, the corresponding change in disposable income inequality tends to be close to zero or slightly negative, indicating the the tax and transfer system plays an important role in cushioning the effects of automation on household disposable income. Isolating the effect of taxes from benefits, we find that benefits do much of the heavy lifting with taxes playing a much more minor role. The effects of the tax system in Western European countries and of both the tax and welfare systems in Eastern European countries are much more muted than the effect of the benefit system in Western Europe. This is in line with the wider literature on stabilising effects of tax-benefit systems in Europe. For example, Dolls, Fuest, et al., 2022 report that income stabilization coefficients range from 20 to 30 percent in some Eastern and Southern European countries to around 60 percent in Belgium, Germany, and Denmark. ¹¹

Taking the example of Germany, automation increases the Gini of individual level market income by 6 per cent between 2006 and 2018. Household formation and the tax system had very little effect on this increase. However, the benefit system more than cushioned this increase so that the corresponding change in the Gini Index of disposable income was a fall of 1 per cent.

¹¹Income stabilization coefficients measure the stabilizing effect of the tax and welfare system for a stylized proportional shock to household market income of 5 percent

Figure 9. The cushioning effect of the tax-benefit system

Notes: The figure shows the change in the Gini Index of market income, of gross income (market income plus welfare) and of net income (market income minus tax). Data: EUROMOD, EU-SILC.

The cushioning effect of the tax-benefit system: 2006 vs 2018

To investigate how the tax-benefit system interacts with automation-driven market income changes, we compare the automation effect shown in Figure 7 to a hypothetical scenario in which an indexed version of the 2006 tax-benefit system was in place in each country.¹² In essence, this shows how discretionary changes to tax and welfare payments between 2006 and 2018 affected the transmission of automation-induced labour income changes into disposable income inequality. The hypothetical effect of automation on income inequality if an indexed 2006 tax-benefit system was in place in 2018 is shown in Figure 10.

In most countries, the transmission of the automation-induced market income changes is slightly lower under the set of 2006 policies. So, for most countries in the sample, changes to the tax and benefit system between 2006 and 2018 have interacted with automation changes in such a way that income inequality has slightly increased. This is particularly visible in Romania, Slovakia and Bulgaria and is in line with the analysis of Paulus and Tasseva, 2020 who show that discretionary changes to benefit policy in these countries during the financial crisis increased net income and decreased income inequality. A notable exception to this pattern is Germany, where automation reduces income inequality under 2018 policies but not under 2006 policies.

¹²This is accomplished by applying the 2006 tax-benefit system to the 2018 population where incomes are deflated by HICP.

Figure 10. Effect of automation on inequality in disposable household income: 2006 vs 2018 tax and benefit policies

Notes: The figure shows the simulated effect of automation on income inequality if an indexed 2006 tax-benefit system was in place in 2018. Data: EUROMOD, EU-SILC.

Isolating the role of differences in absorption of automation shocks - the effect of the German automation shock on inequality

The cross-country differences in automation-driven inequality changes can result from differences in the size of the automation shock - the pace and scale of robot adoption - or from differences in the absorption of the shock. To differentiate between these, for each country we construct a counterfactual scenario - how would income inequality have changed if it had experienced the German automation shock rather than its own, country-specific shock.¹³ This allows a degree of comparison across countries using a common baseline. Figure 11 shows how the country-specific automation shock impacts the Gini Index, above and beyond what we would expect from the German shock.

In general, country-specific market income shocks due to automation are more inequality-increasing than the German shock. This trend is driven by the effect of country-specific automation-induced wage changes (which are more inequality-increasing than German wage changes). Country-specific employment changes tend to counteract this somewhat as they are inequality decreasing compared to German employment changes. All European countries lagged behind Germany in robot adoption in the early 2000s, but most converged to some extent by 2018. Our results suggest that in most countries, rising robot penetration widened inequality more than if they had experienced the German path of automation of more widespread adoption of robots by 2006. Admittedly however, we do not know how this would have changed the path of their income inequality changes prior to 2006.

¹³Germany is the European leader in robot adoption.

Further results from the simulation of this German automation shock are presented in Appendix B. Swapping the 2018 tax-benefit system for an indexed 2006 system affects the transmission of the German shock in a similar manner to the country-specific shock in many countries (Figure B.16). However, in some Eastern European countries (Estonia, Poland and Czechia), 2018 tax and welfare policies cushion the German automation shock by significantly more than 2006 policies. The cushioning of the German automation shock by country-specific household formation and tax-benefit systems is also illustrated in Figure B.17. Household formation amplifies the German automation shock in each country despite the fact that it is inequality decreasing for many country specific shocks. The country-specific tax-benefit systems cushion the German automation shock to a higher extent than they cushion the country-specific shock. Owing to the inequality-increasing nature of the German employment shock, the main driver of this cushioning effect is the benefits system in each country. Taxation plays a more muted role.

Figure 11. Hypothetical effect of the German automation shock on inequality in disposable household income in European countries

Notes: The figure shows the difference between country-specific shock and the German shock for automation-induced wage and employment effect on income inequality. Data: EUROMOD, EU-SILC.

5 Conclusions

In this paper, we have studied the effects of robot exposure on household income inequality in 14 European countries between 2006-2018. We have combined estimating the effects of robot penetration on labor market outcomes (wages and employment rates) with microsimulation models that use these effects as inputs. This allows us to assess the relative role of automation, other market forces, household formation and tax-benefit systems on changes in household income inequality. Our unit of analysis has been a demographic group - we have defined 30 groups per country, based on gender, education, and age, and used IV approach to obtain causal estimates.

We have found that robot exposure had a significant impact on real hourly wages and employment rates, with important differences between regions of Europe. In Western European countries, automation significantly reduced hourly wages and employment rates of more exposed groups. In Eastern European countries, it had no significant effect on labor market outcomes. The resulting effects of robot penetration of changes in labor market outcomes between 2006 and 2018 were more dispersed for men than for women, and for less-educated workers than for more-educated workers.

Using microsimulation models to study the effect of robot-driven shocks on income inequality we have found that, for most countries, automation led to a small increase in income inequality as measured by the Gini index of equivalised, disposable household income. However, compared to overall changes in income inequality in European countries between 2006 and 2018, we have attributed a minor share of these changes to automation. The effect of robot penetration is greatly outweighed by other market income and policy changes over the same time period.

Delving into the mechanics of how automation-driven market income shocks translate into disposable income inequality, we have found that tax-benefit systems provided much cushioning in Western European countries. In general, the benefit systems played a dominant role, owing to the inequality increasing nature of the automation employment shock. We have found a systematic differences between Western and Eastern European countries, with benefit systems cushioning the robot-driven shocks much more in the former. Taxation played a much more muted role, perhaps because wage effects were already inequality decreasing. Household formation also stabilised income inequality, both in Western and Eastern European countries. This means that it is rather rare that several household members have been affected adversely (or positively) by robot-driven shocks. Simulating counterfactual changes in income inequality if the 2006 tax-benefit system was still in place, we find that it would have provided slightly more cushioning than the 2018 tax-benefit system by reducing the transmission of market income changes into disposable income inequality changes.

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Appendix A Sources and descriptive statistics

Table A.1. Variable descriptions

Variable	Description	Source
Socio-demographic characteristics		
Gender	a binary variable describing worker's sex (woman / man)	EU-SES
Education	a categorical variable describing worker's highest level of education completed, three categories: basic education (ISCED 0-2), secondary education (ISCED 3-4), and tertiary education (ISCED 5-8)	EU-SES
Age group	a categorical variable describing worker's age, five categories: 20-29, 30-39, 40-49, 50-59, 60 or more	EU-SES
Dependent Variables		
Change in real hourly wages	difference in log hourly wages (2006-2018)	EU-SES
Group's industry-level exposure		
Automation	difference in the group's exposure to robots (robots per 1,000 workers, 2006-2018)	International Federation of Robotics
Industry shifters	group's exposure to change in log value added (2006-2018)	Eurostat
Relative specialization in routine jobs	relative specialization of a group g in industry i 's routine jobs in 2006	EU-SES
Industry labour share decline	group's exposure to change in labour share (2006-2018)	Eurostat
Offshoring	difference in the group's exposure to offshoring measured as foreign value added in gross output (2006-2018)	OECD TIVA Indicators
Chinese imports penetration	difference in the group's exposure to the Chinese import penetration following Acemoglu, Autor, et al. (2016): change in import from China (2006-2018) divided by initial absorption (industry outputs plus industry imports minus industry exports)	OECD TIVA Indicators
Other variables		
Manufacturing share	group's wage share in manufacturing in 2006	EU-SES
Minimum wage bite	the number of workers with wages in 2006 below the 2018 minimum wage level divided by the number of all workers	EU-SES
Population change	change in log population of a group (2006-2018)	Eurostat
Employment rate change	change in employment rate of a group (2006-2018)	Eurostat

Notes: Description of variables used in the analysis.

Table A.2. Descriptive statistics

	Obs.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min.	Max.
Gender: woman	420	0.49	0.50	0.00	1.00
Gender: man	420	0.51	0.50	0.00	1.00
Basic education	420	0.15	0.36	0.00	1.00
Secondary education	420	0.55	0.50	0.00	1.00
Tertiary education	420	0.30	0.46	0.00	1.00
Age: 20-29	420	0.19	0.39	0.00	1.00
Age: 30-39	420	0.27	0.44	0.00	1.00
Age: 40-49	420	0.28	0.45	0.00	1.00
Age: 50-59	420	0.22	0.42	0.00	1.00
Age: 60+	420	0.05	0.21	0.00	1.00
Log wage growth	420	0.25	0.30	-0.48	1.23
Automation	420	0.82	0.59	0.01	2.44
Industry shifters	420	0.19	0.16	-0.14	0.68
Industry labor share change	420	0.06	0.09	-0.18	0.33
Offshoring	420	0.01	0.01	-0.02	0.11
Chinese imports penetration	420	0.01	0.02	-0.00	0.18
Manufacturing share	420	0.26	0.13	0.02	0.67
Routine tasks	420	1.00	0.40	0.12	2.72
Log income growth	330	0.69	0.64	-0.14	2.30
Employment rate change	420	0.04	0.07	-0.21	0.26
Minimum wage bite	420	0.39	0.31	0.00	1.00
Population change	420	-0.05	0.38	-2.10	1.14

Notes: This table presents the following statistics for each variable: Number of Observations, Average Value, Standard Deviation, Maximum and Minimum Value. The sources and description of the variables can be found in Table A.1.

Figure A.1. Automation and income growth in Europe

Notes: Figures show relationship between adjusted penetration of robots and real total disposable household income (residualized after controlling for country fixed effects) for demographic groups in 18 countries. Panel A plots the relationship for Western European countries (France, Germany, Netherlands, Finland, Norway, Sweden). Panel B plots the relationship for Eastern European countries (Bulgaria, Czechia, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Slovakia). Marker sizes indicate the within-country employment shares of demographic groups. Data: EU-SES.

Figure A.2. Automation and employment rate change in Europe

Notes: Figures show relationship between adjusted penetration of robots and employment rates (residualized after controlling for country fixed effects) for demographic groups in 18 countries. Panel A plots the relationship for Western European countries (France, Germany, Netherlands, Finland, Norway, Sweden). Panel B plots the relationship for Eastern European countries (Bulgaria, Czechia, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Slovakia). Marker sizes indicate the within-country employment shares of demographic groups. Data: EU-SES.

Appendix B Additional results

Table B.1. Automation and changes in real hourly wages - IV first stage results

	(1) Automation*Western Europe	(2) Automation*Eastern Europe
Automation (IV)*Western Europe	0.426*** (0.029)	0.029 (0.022)
Automation (IV)*Eastern Europe	-0.067*** (0.015)	0.392*** (0.030)
Country FE	yes	yes
Manufacturing share	yes	yes
Gender	yes	yes
Education	yes	yes
Routine tasks	yes	yes
Industry shifters	yes	yes
F-statistic first stage	65.89	65.89
Observations	420	420

Notes: Table reports the first stage for our baseline IV estimation. The dependent variable is the change in log wages for each group from 2006 to 2018. In all regressions, we control for manufacturing share of employment, gender, education, relative specialization in routine tasks, industry shifters and country fixed effects. All regressions are weighted by the share of the country's employment. Robust standard errors are reported.

Data: EU-SES. * p<.10; ** p<.05; *** p<.01

Table B.2. Automation and changes in real hourly wages - additional controls, 2006-2018

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)
	2SLS	2SLS	2SLS	2SLS	2SLS	2SLS	2SLS
Automation*Western Europe	-0.125*** (0.024)	-0.110*** (0.023)	-0.129*** (0.026)	-0.126*** (0.024)	-0.070** (0.028)	-0.127*** (0.024)	-0.069** (0.028)
Automation*Eastern Europe	0.039 (0.030)	0.024 (0.029)	0.040 (0.029)	0.023 (0.030)	0.008 (0.029)	0.027 (0.030)	-0.019 (0.030)
Country FE	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Manufacturing share	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Gender	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Education	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Routine tasks	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Industry shifters	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes	yes
Industry labor share change	no	yes	no	no	no	no	yes
Offshoring	no	no	yes	no	no	no	yes
Chinese imports penetration	no	no	no	yes	no	no	yes
Minimum wage bite	no	no	no	no	yes	no	yes
Population change	no	no	no	no	no	yes	yes
F-statistic first stage	65.89	62.92	66.33	61.50	66.63	65.19	57.19
Observations	420	420	420	420	420	420	420

Notes: Table shows estimates of the relationship between task displacement due to automation and the change in log wages across 30 demographic groups in 18 European countries. The dependent variable is the change in log wages for each group from 2006 to 2018. In all regressions, we control for manufacturing share of employment, gender, education, relative specialization in routine tasks, industry shifters and country fixed effects. All regressions are weighted by the share of the country's employment. Column 1 shows our baseline estimates. In column 2, we additionally control for the increase in the exposure to offshoring. In column 3, we additionally control for the Chinese imports penetration. In column 4, we additionally control for minimum wage bite. In column 5, we additionally control for population change. The sources and description of the variables can be found in Table A.1. Robust standard errors are reported.

Data: EU-SES. * p<.10; ** p<.05; *** p<.01

Figure B.1. Distribution of wage changes due to automation, by gender

Notes: Figures shows the distribution of wage changes due to automation for demographic groups. Wage changes due to automation are calculated by multiplying the group’s exposure to automation by the wage effects of automation from the equation 4. We plot the distribution for the restricted sample of groups representing at least 1% of countries’ employment.
Data: EU-SES.

Figure B.2. Distribution of wage changes due to automation, by education

Notes: Figures shows the distribution of wage changes due to automation for demographic groups. Wage changes due to automation are calculated by multiplying the group’s exposure to automation by the wage effects of automation from the equation 4. We plot the distribution for the restricted sample of groups representing at least 1% of countries’ employment.
Data: EU-SES.

Figure B.3. Distribution of wage changes due to automation, by age

Notes: Figures shows the distribution of wage changes due to automation for demographic groups. Wage changes due to automation are calculated by multiplying the group's exposure to automation by the wage effects of automation from equation 4. We plot the distribution for the restricted sample of groups representing at least 1% of countries' employment.
Data: EU-SES.

Figure B.4. Distribution of wage changes due to automation: countries (i.)

Notes: Figures shows the distribution of wage changes due to automation for demographic groups. Wage changes due to automation are calculated by multiplying the group's exposure to automation by the wage effects of automation from the equation 4.

Data: EU-SES.

Figure B.5. Distribution of wage changes due to automation: countries (ii.)

Notes: Figures shows the distribution of wage changes due to automation for demographic groups. Wage changes due to automation are calculated by multiplying the group's exposure to automation by the wage effects of automation from the equation 4.
Data: EU-SES.

Figure B.6. Distribution of employment changes due to automation, by gender

Notes: Figures shows the distribution of employment changes due to automation for demographic groups. employment changes due to automation are calculated by multiplying the group's exposure to automation by the employment effects of automation. We plot the distribution for the restricted sample of groups representing at least 1% of countries' employment.
Data: EU-SES.

Figure B.7. Distribution of employment changes due to automation, by education

Notes: Figures shows the distribution of employment changes due to automation for demographic groups. employment changes due to automation are calculated by multiplying the group's exposure to automation by the employment effects of automation. We plot the distribution for the restricted sample of groups representing at least 1% of countries' employment.

Data: EU-SES.

Figure B.8. Distribution of employment changes due to automation, by age

Notes: Figures shows the distribution of employment changes due to automation for demographic groups. employment changes due to automation are calculated by multiplying the group's exposure to automation by the employment effects of automation. We plot the distribution for the restricted sample of groups representing at least 1% of countries' employment.

Data: EU-SES.

Figure B.9. Distribution of employment changes due to automation: countries (i.)

Notes: Figures shows the distribution of employment changes due to automation for demographic groups. employment changes due to automation are calculated by multiplying the group's exposure to automation by the employment effects of automation.

Data: EU-SES.

Figure B.10. Distribution of employment changes due to automation: countries (ii.)

Notes: Figures shows the distribution of employment changes due to automation for demographic groups. employment changes due to automation are calculated by multiplying the group's exposure to automation by the employment effects of automation.

Data: EU-SES.

Table B.3. Wage and employment changes due to automation

	Western Europe		Eastern Europe	
	Low wage (mean)	High wage (mean)	Low wage (mean)	High wage (mean)
Automation	1.14	0.82	0.90	0.55
Wage change due to automation	-0.14	-0.10	0.03	0.02
Employment change due to automation	-0.10	-0.07	-0.03	-0.02

Notes: Table shows the average exposure to automation, wage and employment changes due to automation for demographic groups. Low wage groups are the groups with 2006 average wages below or equal to the country median. High wage groups are the groups with 2006 average wages above the country median.

Data: EU-SES.

Figure B.11. Wage changes due to automation and initial wage levels

Notes: Figure shows the distribution of wage changes due to automation for demographic groups. Wage changes due to automation are calculated by multiplying the group's increase in the exposure to automation by the wage effects of automation from the equation 4. We plot the distribution for the restricted sample of groups representing at least 1% of the countries' employment.
Data: EU-SES.

Figure B.12. Wage changes due to automation and initial wage levels by country

Notes: Data: EU-SES.

Figure B.13. Wage changes due to automation and initial wage levels by country

Notes: Data: EU-SES.

Table B.4. Automation and changes in income in the U.S.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
	Hourly wage	Ind. market income	HH market income	HH disposable income
Automation	-0.034*** (0.004)	-0.022 (0.014)	-0.031*** (0.007)	-0.019*** (0.006)
Manufacturing share	yes	yes	yes	yes
Gender	yes	yes	yes	yes
Education	yes	yes	yes	yes
Industry shifters	yes	yes	yes	yes
Adj. R-squared	0.79	0.72	0.70	0.67
Mean of outcome	0.05	0.10	0.33	0.31
Mean of automation	4.68	4.68	4.68	4.68
Observations	500	500	500	500

Notes: Table shows estimates of the relationship between penetration of robots and the change in measures of income across 500 demographic groups in the U.S. In column 1, the dependent variable is the change in log hourly wages for each group from 1980 to 2016. In column 2, the dependent variable is the change in log per capita individual market income for each group from 1980 to 2016. In column 3, the dependent variable is the log per capita household market income change for each group from 1980 to 2016. In column 4, the dependent variable is the log per capita household total disposable income change for each group from 1980 to 2016. Penetration of robots, manufacturing share, and industry shifters are taken from Acemoglu and Restrepo (2022). All regressions are weighted by the share of hours worked by each group in 1980. Robust standard errors are reported. Data: US Census (1980) and the American Community Survey (2014-2018). * $p < .10$; ** $p < .05$; *** $p < .01$

Figure B.14. Wage inequality changes due to automation

Notes: Figure shows the difference between the actual level of wage inequality and wage inequality levels in the counterfactual scenario with no changes in automation.
Data: EU-SES.

Figure B.15. Effect of German automation on inequality in disposable household income

Notes: The figure shows the four terms of the decomposition of the change in household income inequality (automation-induced wage effect, automation-induced employment effect, other market effects, policy effect).
Data: EUROMOD, EU-SILC.

Figure B.16. Effect of German automation on inequality in disposable household income: 2006 vs 2018 tax and benefit policies

Notes: The figure shows the four terms of the decomposition of the change in household income inequality and the hypothetical effect of automation on income inequality if an indexed 2006 tax-benefit system was in place in 2018. Data: EUROMOD, EU-SILC.

Figure B.17. The cushioning effect of the tax-benefit system - German automation shock

Notes: The figure shows the change in the Gini Index of market income, of gross income (market income plus welfare) and of net income (market income minus tax). Data: EUROMOD, EU-SILC.

Appendix C Coverage of employment in small firms

The EU-SES coverage is limited to firms with at least 10 workers. The EU-SES does not include workers from small firms, nor self-employed individuals who comprise a substantial share of employment in some cells (see Figure C.1). This is important for our study, as automation technologies such as robots are more often used in larger firms. Hence, workers in our EU-SES sample have a larger exposure to robots than workers in smaller firms. As a consequence, we may overestimate the wage effects.

Figure C.1. Small firm employment, and self-employment (% of total employment)

Notes: Figure shows fraction of workers working in small firms or as self-employed for 450 socio-demographic groups.

Data: EU-SES.